

Conservative management of myocardial lesions secondary to stable penetrating precordial trauma with a positive pericardial window by thoracoscopy, clinical case report

Manejo conservador de lesiones miocárdicas secundarias a trauma precordial penetrante estable con ventana pericárdica positiva por toracoscopia, reporte de caso clínico

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Abstract

Penetrating precordial injuries are becoming more frequent. Of every 100 patients with these injuries and hemodynamically stable, 15%-20% have an occult heart injury. If the pleura has been violated, the pericardial window can be performed subxiphoid, laparoscopic with a trans diaphragmatic window, or thoracoscopic. The objective of the study is: to describe the case of a patient with conservative management of myocardial injury secondary to penetrating precordial trauma by a sharp weapon, with a positive pericardial window by thoracoscopy.

Clinical case: A 36-year-old male patient, with no pathological history, was admitted to the Teófilo Dávila Machala-Ecuador General Hospital, with a diagnosis of penetrating chest trauma plus penetrating precordial wound, hemodynamically stable.

Evolution: A conservative management of the myocardial lesion was performed, after a positive pericardial window by thoracoscopy plus thoracostomy, after four days of hospitalization he was discharged with favorable evolution. There were no complications or re-admission after 3 months of monitoring and control by external consultation.

Conclusion: In hemodynamically stable patients with penetrating precordial wounds and a positive pericardial window who present cardiac injury without active bleeding, are amenable to conservative management, this is a minimally invasive alternative that is less morbid and as safe as open techniques.

Keywords: Pericardial Window, Cardiac Trauma, Conservative Management.

Resumen

Las heridas precordiales penetrantes son cada vez más frecuentes. De cada 100 pacientes con estas heridas y hemodinámicamente estables, el 15%-20% tienen herida oculta del corazón. La ventana pericárdica puede realizarse subxifoidea, laparoscópica con ventana transdiafragmática o toracoscópica, si la pleura ha sido violada. El Objetivo del estudio es: describir el caso de un paciente con Manejo conservador de lesión miocárdica secundaria a trauma precordial penetrante por arma cortopunzante, con ventana pericárdica positiva por toracoscopia.

Caso clínico: Paciente de 36 años, de sexo masculino, sin antecedentes patológicos, ingresado en el hospital general Teófilo Dávila Machala-Ecuador, con diagnóstico de trauma penetrante de tórax más herida precordial penetrante, hemodinámicamente estable.

Evolución: Se realizó manejo conservador de la lesión miocárdica, posterior a una ventana pericárdica positiva por toracoscopia más toracostomía, luego de cuatro días de hospitalización es dado de alta médica con evolución favorable. No hubo complicaciones, ni reingreso posterior a 3 meses de seguimiento y control por consulta externa.

Conclusión: En pacientes hemodinámicamente estables con heridas precordiales penetrantes y ventana pericárdica positiva que presentan lesión cardíaca sin sangrado activo, son susceptibles de manejo conservador, ésta es una alternativa mínimamente invasiva que resulta menos mórbida y tan segura como las técnicas abiertas.

Palabras clave: Ventana Pericardica, Trauma Cardíaco, Manejo Conservador.

Until the 9th century, penetrating cardiac injuries were considered lethal and intractable, but in 1896 the German surgeon Ludwig Rhen reported the first successful repair of a stab wound to the right ventricle on its second day of evolution. Over the next 10 years, Rhen collected 124 patients who had suffered penetrating cardiac injuries, resulting in 40% mortality.

Until the early 1980s, all hemodynamically stable patients with penetrating precordial trauma were studied by means of an exploratory thoracotomy¹.

A penetrating wound is a deep wound with loss of tissue, caused by a sharp object that, although small in diameter and does not appear serious, requires medical treatment.

Penetrating precordial injuries are becoming more frequent. Of every 100 patients with these injuries, and hemodynamically stable, 15%-20% have an occult heart injury. Penetrating chest trauma represents 10% of mortality worldwide, reaching up to 82% in developing countries². Due to its characteristics and particularly its high mortality, penetrating cardiac trauma (CPT) constitutes a permanent emergency challenge³.

It is estimated that 94% of patients with cardiac trauma die on the scene or during transport and only 10 to 20% of these patients arrive alive at the hospital, and of these, 17% to 58% die, constituting a high rate of death. hospital mortality^{4,5}.

It is known that up to 20% of hemodynamically stable patients presenting with chest trauma due to a sharp stab wound present occult lesions in the heart. Only 60% of patients with hemopericardium present Beck's triad (distension of the neck veins, hypotension, and muffled heart sounds. One-third of patients with penetrating heart injuries are hemodynamically stable, becoming a diagnostic dilemma and a challenge for the surgeon^{6,7}.

Precordial, trans mediastinal, neck, or upper abdominal lesions may have symptoms, electrocardiograms, and/or radiology (chest X-ray and ultrasound) that show a cardiac lesion. Ultrasound continues to be a fundamental tool for the evaluation of a patient with trauma, used since 1990, which constitutes a standard diagnostic modality, a positive result is an indication for a surgical procedure by thoracotomy or sternotomy and cardiac exploration; however, there may be false negatives^{6,8,9}.

Despite the great utility of ultrasound as a diagnostic tool for hemopericardium due to cardiac injury; there may be false negatives, as reported in a prospective study published in 2015 by a group from South Africa, where Nicol

et al., found an 86.7% sensitivity of ultrasound, limited mainly by hemothorax and air in the pericardial sac, being surpassed by the laparoscopic pericardial window in stable patients with occult cardiac injuries^{6,9}.

Previously, the management algorithm for penetrating cardiac injuries in hemodynamically stable patients required immediate sternotomy and cardiac exploration^{5,10}. This traditional invasive management is associated with comorbidities, in addition to a frequency of blank procedures that calls attention to the need to adhere to other less invasive and morbid management possibilities that are currently offered by advances in diagnostic and therapeutic imaging technologies, in addition, more exhaustive hemodynamic monitoring⁴. As another alternative, the Subxiphoid pericardial window, laparoscopic with trans diaphragmatic window, or thoracoscopic may be performed if the pleura has been violated. When the window is positive, the protocol is thoracostomy or sternotomy; many of these surgeries are non-therapeutic since small non-bleeding myocardial lesions are found.

Complications such as cardiac arrest and sepsis are seen with greater severity in patients with sternotomy. Hospital stays and stays in the ICU are significantly lower in the pericardial drainage group than in those who undergo sternotomy⁵.

Presenting the experience of conservative management of cardiac trauma is highly relevant, to eliminate paradigms about its management, since, despite the update and the new tendency to be conservative in all scenarios, approaches are still being practiced in many centers. more aggressive surgical procedures that in some cases lead to necessary morbidity and non-therapeutic surgeries.

Therefore, in the importance of managing patients with this type of trauma, it is considered essential to contribute to the scientific community in the field of health., when describing the case of a patient with conservative management of myocardial injury secondary to penetrating precordial trauma by a sharp weapon, with a positive pericardial window by thoracoscopy, evidencing a thoracotomy or sternotomy with the comorbidities that this implies.

CLINICAL CASE

A 36-year-old male patient, of mixed ethnicity, with no pathological history of interest, who presented with multiple injuries to the chest by a sharp weapon, Presents three wounds of approximately 2.5cm each, the first at the level of the fifth right parasternal intercostal space, another in the sixth right intercostal space, midclavicular line and a third wound in the seventh intercostal space behind the rear axillary line; patient diagnosed with Grade II right hemothorax with a collection of approximately 300cc, with a 2.5cm lesion at the level of the middle lung lobe, with active bleeding, who remains hemodynamically stable; come aAt the Teófilo Dávila

General Hospital in the city of Machala, Ecuador, with a diagnosis of penetrating chest trauma plus a penetrating precordial injury, a chest drain was placed initially.

On physical exam: antalgic patient, uncooperative, with a patent airway, previously described chest wounds with active bleeding at the time of examination, on auscultation, left lung field with good ventilation, right lung field absence of noise at the lung base level, on palpation of the soft and depressible abdomen without apparent pathology, inguinal-genital región, and extremities without alteration, patient with Glasgow 15.

Blood pressure: 110/80 mmHg, heart rate: 105 beats per minute, respiratory rate: 24 per minute, temperature: 36 degrees Celsius, O2 saturation 97%

Analytical chemistry: Leukocytes 11.65 mm³; Neutrophils 65.4; Lymphocytes 25.9%; Hemoglobin 11.1 g/dL; hematocrit 37.4%; Plates 185 mm³; Tp 11.8 seconds, Ttp 22.8 seconds, Prothrombin Act 129.7, INR 0.94, Glucose 179 mg/dL; Urea 28.4 mg/dL; Creatinine 0.74 mg/dL.

Complementary tests: Standard chest X-ray which shows grade II right hemothorax.

Evolution

For the treatment of the case, the following procedure is carried out:

- The chest tube previously placed in the emergency room was removed and the incision was widened until obtaining one of approximately 2.5cm (Image 1), through which the 30-degree optic was introduced and the cavity was reviewed by means of diagnostic thoracoscopy. right, where hemothorax of approximately 300cc is evidenced, plus grade II pulmonary trauma, the diaphragm is explored to find compensation.

Image 1. Removal of the chest tube.

- Subsequently, a pericardial window was performed with a positive result. by thoracoscopy plus pulmonary raffia, where hemothorax is evidenced, plus grade II lung injury, plus grade II cardiac trauma, with injury to the right atrium, a Maryland clamp is passed and the pericardium is clamped (Image 2).

Image 2. Pericardial clamping

- Then proceed with pericardiotomy with the help of Metzembau scissors, leakage of hematic fluid is evidenced, the Grade II myocardial lesion is identified, located in the right atrium (Image 3), the clot was removed, plus lavage with 1000cc warm saline without evidence of active bleeding (Image 4), no hemostats, sealants, or sutures were removed at the cardiac level.

Image 3. Pericardiotomy

Image 4. Washing the wound with saline solution

The photographs were taken by the surgical team during the procedure.

- The instruments were withdrawn, and raffia of the lung wound was performed, a thoracostomy was left with the placement of an N 30 chest tube connected to a water intrapleural drainage, and the procedure is terminated.
- The patient goes to recovery and then to hospitalization, management of the chest tube is given for 48 hours whose output was less than 100cc/24 hours, with a control chest X-ray in which expanded lungs are observed.

The procedure was carried out without any complications, it did not require intermediate or intensive care, and the clinical management of the patient was conservative, 2 days after the procedure is removed the tube, a normal control echocardiogram, favorable evolution and on the fourth day of hospitalization he was discharged. There were no complications or readmission after 3 months of monitoring and control by external consultation.

Discussion

Penetrating cardiac injuries are a public health problem, representing one of the major causes of death due to urban violence in young people. My primary site of myocardial injury is the free wall of the right ventricle¹¹ and it constitutes a challenge since it requires rapid surgical management to prevent its outcome from being fatal¹². A great deal of experience in the treatment of these injuries has been demonstrated over the years since the first attempts at cardiac wound repair by Cappelen, Farina, Rehn, and Hill.

The clinical presentation of patients with penetrating cardiac trauma can be variable: lifeless, critically unstable, cardiac tamponade, thoracoabdominal injury, and benign lesions reported from 15% to 30%^{8,9}.

In a study with 220 patients with penetrating precordial trauma, 95% were a male, mean age of 30.4 ± 13.3 and a median of 27 years. Mechanism: Aggression (91.8%). The traumatic agent was cold steel 84.4% and firearm 9.5%. The approach was sternotomy in 71.4% and left thoracotomy in 26.4%. The most common lesioned areas were the right ventricle 50%, and the left ventricle 32.7%. The median postoperative stay was 6 days (2). As in Colombia, it was evidenced that 240 patients with penetrating cardiac injury, 96.2% male, mean age 27.8 years, and overall mortality of 14.6%, 41.2% corresponding to firearm injury and 11.7% to wounds sharp short¹³. Data related to the case under study, a 36-year-old male patient who suffered a cardiac penetrating injury due to a cold steel attack in the right costal region, hospitalization time 5 days.

García A.³ presents a study with 14 patients with pericardial effusion identified on ultrasound, four close clinical observations, and follow-up with daily ultrasounds. None deteriorated, required surgical intervention, or presented at 28-day follow-up. Also, and a 2021 meta-analysis comparing ultrasonography and pericardial window in stable patients, a 79% sensitivity and 92% specificity for chest ultrasonography emerged¹⁴. Despite the great utility of ultrasound as a diagnostic tool for hemopericardium due to cardiac injury; there may be false negatives, as reported in a prospective study published in 2015 by a group from South Africa, where Nicol et al., found an 86.7% sensitivity of ultrasound, limited mainly by hemothorax and air in the pericardial sac, being surpassed by the laparoscopic pericardial window in stable patients with occult cardiac injuries^{6,15}. It can also be related to the case, where follow-up is carried out 30 days after the intervention through control ultrasounds and no complications are reported.

The time required to perform a pericardial window is currently considered to be 24 to 48 hours with the patient

stable to consider favorable results^{5,8}. The Trauma and Emergency Surgery group of Cali in 2021 proposes the Management Algorithm for penetrating cardiac injuries, in hemodynamically stable patients, divided into the severity of the hemopericardium, requiring pericardial window for those with moderate or severe, performing only lavage and management of associated injuries if there is no active bleeding, in which case a sternotomy or thoracotomy will be performed depending on each situation¹⁶. A similar situation arises from Andrade et al.⁷, in their case report article, where he describes that after the presentation of a positive pericardial window in penetrating trauma in the precordial area, performs pericardiectomy as there is no active bleeding, performs saline irrigation with a nelaton tube and inserts a 30° lens by video thoracoscopy, with the conclusion: non-bleeding laceration of the pericardium, minor lesion in the fat surrounding the right coronary artery, concluding that it was an injury that did not require any surgical procedure on the heart. In our case, a 30-degree optic was introduced and the cavity was reviewed by thoracoscopy, drainage, and saline lavage of the cavity.

Pericardoscopy should now be considered a diagnostic tool for cardiothoracic and trauma surgeons⁸. In relation to this, Berg, et al.¹⁷, determined that surgical intervention was only necessary for 14% of 543 patients with penetrating chest wounds, therefore laparoscopy is included as an essential tool to rule out cardiac injury without increasing morbidity with unnecessary surgery.

Pericardial drainage alone appears to be safe and effective in the management of penetrating chest trauma, but this is a decision that should be made in a trauma center with experience in the management of cardiac injury and the availability of early surgery⁹. This coincides with the management carried out in the patient under study, where the initial treatment was in an emergency with the placement of a pericardial drainage treatment. Also, in the controlled trials carried out by Nycol et al., the efficacy and safety of hemopericardium drainage is determined, avoiding a necessary sternotomy for hemodynamically stable patients⁵. It is considered that the choice of treatment arising from the situation to be treated, the hemodynamic status of the patient, and the number of lesions produced¹¹.

Patients with penetrating chest trauma and a positive pericardial window have been managed surgically in most cases, being part of algorithms in many therapeutic guidelines, however, this type of management has been left to those who really need it, since many patients benefit from conservative management, avoiding surgeries with high non-therapeutic morbidity.

In hemodynamically stable patients with a positive pericardial window by thoracoscopy who present cardiac injury without active bleeding, are susceptible to conservative management. This is a minimally invasive alternative that is less morbid and as safe as open techniques.

The case of a 36-year-old male patient with penetrating cardiac lesions is described, in which a pericardial window was performed by thoracoscopy, where a lesion was evidenced in the right atrium, after lavage with saline solution the clot was removed without evidence of bleeding. active, no sealing hemostats or sutures were obtained at the cardiac level. With favorable evolution and follow-up.

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PB, JV, AF, MG, DV: design, analysis, and interpretation of the data, drafting of the manuscript, and approval of the final version.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval and participation consent

The authors have the patient's informed consent for the publication of the clinical case and its images.

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